

“The Chicken is Very Thin.”

A Part of the Neolithic Message at the Bosphorus Summit 2023

Hans Georg K. Gebel

This contribution¹ deals with questions of the Neolithic legacy in the behavioural systems of us modern productive humans, or, in other words, with the confined human dispositions established by Neolithisation and their technological, socioeconomic and cognitive significances today. I presented the topic in the shape of theses-type statements, serving a panel at the 14th Bosphorus Summit² 2023 (Istanbul, 16-17 November 2023) entitled *The Consequences of Neolithic Lifeways*. The Bosphorus Summit 2023 brought together numerous keynote speeches and panels addressing topics related to the summit’s title *Navigating the Next Century. Challenges and Promises*³.

My concise Istanbul Statements (*cf.* below) were divided into two groups: Statements 1-7 (The Neolithic Legacy) represent the fundamentally changed lifeways characterised by growth- and security-oriented producing behaviour that were passed on to us modern humans with Neolithisation, Statements 8-12 (The Neolithic Consequences) representing the fundamental lessons to be learned from Neolithisation today. The statements were formulated in a theses-type way to be comprehensible to an audience of political, economic and military decision-makers with no substantial knowledge of archaeology and anthropology. The statements attempt to ‘translate’ Neolithic findings for the con-texts and understanding of current ways of thinking and living in – especially – the Global South. In addition, they are intended to present a general socio-political essence from current Neolithisation research in the Middle East – and my elaboration for our modern ethos as being the latest state of the productive human being, or the world’s now dominating socioeconomic phenotype, the Homo neolithicus.

The following section (Onboarding the Subject) ‘responds’ to the potential academic critique of politicisations of the Neolithic, which I only briefly referred to in my Istanbul presentation.

Onboarding the Subject Academically

The following Comments 1-4 are presented here for critics who still see prehistoric research as capable of

being apolitical and who neglect archaeo-political mandates⁴.

The derivation of concerns and recommendations from Neolithic research for our modern development indeed represents a politicisation of the Neolithic. In my view, they follow an ethical duty of our archaeological disciplines, which they have beyond empirical research (see also Knapp and Ashmore 1999; van der Leeuw 2007; Kristiansen 2014; Hodder 2018; EAA 2021). The scientific justifiability of such derivations and their dangers of serving ideologised interests are discussed in Gebel 2021. However, with a clear decoupling of empirical results and ‘translated’ lessons from the past for our present and future, such statements seem permissible and ethical duty for us professionals, also representing a ‘natural mandate’ of the archaeologists.

We should consider that empirical Neolithic results are also

1. fundamentally influenced by the personalities of the researchers, their research milieus and their political environments. Their dispositions should always be disclosed so that their epistemological foundations, contexts and validities become transparent.
2. By ‘translating’ Neolithic results for understanding modern contexts, we are leaving the realm of prehistoric research and following the imperative to draw lessons from the past and to make our research applicable for the benefit of people today. Many colleagues still view this imperative critically or even as illegitimate because it can hardly or not at all fulfil scientific criteria – which is true for many conclusions we have in historical sciences. Such arguments often go hand in hand with the idea that archaeology and archaeological results are, *per se*, or have to be apolitical and neutral and that empirical results are/ can be fundamentally valid despite the frequent lack of epistemic transparency and a lack of testability in humanities. Other arguments against the translation of lessons from the past can be: the dangers of instrumentalisations of archaeological research, *e.g.* for political and territorial claims and conflicts; the manipulation/ falsification of history; ethical dangers such as cultural appropriation or the reproduction of colonial patterns; etc. These risks exist in principle but

are considered to be low or less relevant in the case of the Neolithic Legacy.

3. I locate the translation and archaeopolitical use of the Neolithic Legacy for us modern in the fields of an Applied Archaeology (unlike Political Archaeology), which only exists in this sense with alternative specialist understanding (*cf.* some of the references). The errors and fallacies inherent in general archaeological research also apply to the translation and use of the Neolithic Legacy and its archaeopolitical perspectives (Gebel 2021); however, this does not make translations of the past for the present and future illegitimate *per se*.

4. It becomes problematic when archaeopolitical 'translations' flow back into the empirical research process, resulting in a 'heuristic contamination' of primary data. Although interest-led 'contamination' of primary data is commonplace in archaeological research, it is even more so when empirical research is manipulated by archaeopolitical 'translations'.

For everything, even for research, it is true that we only recognise what we see or have experienced – or are in the process of recognising¹. Translated into the apparent inability of humans to learn lessons from history sustainably (*cf.* Kahneman 2011), this would mean that if our generations cannot perceive the lessons that history offers due to cognitive distortions, emotional attachments and a lack of reflection, then this has a lot to do with the inability to incorporate only what we have experienced ourselves into our experiences and knowledge and therefore cannot apply the lessons from the cyclical elements of history. Accordingly, the basic thesis is that our present-day experiences with disastrous developments are part of a (pre-) historic cyclicity, which repeats itself differently and at seemingly more complex levels – with principally the same undesirable patterns. Did this cyclicity emerge with the ethos of the producing human beings, *i.e.* the Neolithic, and from then became inherent in their evolutionary fate? For aspects of these thoughts *cf.* also Fischer 1970, MacMillan 2008 or Connerton 1989.

However, the fact that a world forum is inviting archaeologists to report on the consequences of a prehistoric transition and suspecting that the occurrence of confined/ sedentary territoriality, technological innovation and wealth disparity may have had crucial consequences for us modern is remarkable and, if continued, a good start for public learning from the past.

The Concise Istanbul Statements on the Neolithic Legacy. Presented at the Bosphorus Summit, Istanbul, 16th Nov. 2023

Although the section was very well attended, and the audience asked interesting questions, there was no

broader discussion of the statements. In addition to the section's time constraints, this could have been due to the political exposure questions that would have been required and the unfamiliar topic.

The Neolithic Legacy

1) Neolithisations are processes in human evolution during which producing behaviour established value-creating cognitive environments (commodification regimes), often related to the emergence of settled life or other forms of confined physical and mental territorialities; they represent the fundamental transition from taking (foraging social environments) to making (confined productive social environments), and changed man's cognitive dispositions fundamentally. Productivity created fundamental self-progressing complexities and constraints promoting and differentiating surplus and commodity needs, food and social security, etc., beyond the ultimate life essentials. On the other hand, such productive systems became more vulnerable due to their complexities; they had to be secured and defended more intensively. (*Neolithic Productivity*)

2) Neolithisations occurred globally and supra-regionally at different times in different contexts and regions, upon the coincidence of supporting regional and supra-regional surplus triggers and ingredients and by using different constituents (*e.g.* domesticates, abiotic resources, productive food and craft technologies, cognitive frameworks). (*Neolithic Polycentrism and Diversity*)

3) The grammars of Neolithisations behave ever-adaptive, expansive and sometimes stagnant or regressive upon internal and external natural and socio-economic stress/ pressure; their often similar mechanisms follow regionally and supra-regionally differentiated specifics. (*Neolithic Grammar*)

4) The shared critical elements/ traits of all Neolithisations are the sustainable development of productive behaviour and continuous safeguarding of growth (or at least sustaining the achieved) in all areas of life (technological, social, economic and cognitive), especially regarding food and territorial security (ideological territories included). Nature becomes increasingly subject to unsustainable exploitation/ depletion, and differentiation and hierarchisation gain central functions in many life spheres (settlement patterns, social and work structures, gender?). (*Neolithic Innovation and Growth*)

5) Once productive dispositions started to rule human behaviour and its all-level exchange with internal and external neighbours, ideological and societal diversification was increasingly needed to sustain hierarchical social, economic, and ideological (ritually and symbolically supported) cohesion systems. (*Neolithic Cognition*)

6) The corporate creation and maintenance of sustainable values (social, economic and ideological commodifications) and the confinement of productive resources (habitats, labour, commodity differentiation, economic and ideological territories) become the main reasons for various types of competition, social differentiation/ hierarchisation (e.g. elitism, gender diversity, social violence), higher levels of organised aggression/ conflict management, uncontrolled productivity/ progressive prosperity/ population dynamics and related acceleration and agglomeration/ aggregation phenomena. (*Neolithic Aggregation and Acceleration*)

7) The failure and collapse of Neolithic developments are caused by systems that have become too sensitive and too complex for coping with fast and complex growth/ changes and could not react in time successfully enough to (blends of) undesirable developments. Occurring outside interests/ aggression and the impacts of shifting local/ regional diversification, hierarchies, competencies and/ or competition gain relevance in weakening the resilience of local/ regional systems. (*Neolithic Regression and Collapse*)

The Neolithic Consequences for us Modern

8) Today's productive humans carry the Neolithic behaviour within them; this heritage makes us the current variant of the Neolithic human socioeconomic and cognitive phenotype in all its modern regional forms. (*Neolithic Legacy in Us Modern*)

9) It is one of the universal features of this historic productive human disposition to ignore lessons of the past and to sustain primarily the immediate confined interests and security of their own group. Generalised care or reciprocities are practised only if they sustain own systems/ regimes. (*Historical Ignorance of Us Modern*)

10) Archeologists and all historians have a moral duty – and the “natural” mandate – to translate lessons from the past. Due to 9), they regularly are unsuccessful in conveying historical messages or appealing to a historical mind in modern decision-making. The mandate's implementation must come along with raising societal awareness of historical failures and aberrations. (*Archaeologist's Responsibility and Advocacy*)

11) The Neolithic past and the succeeding productive and stratified societies bequeathed us several critical behavioural fields, which were – from then on – inscribed in our human ethos. Sustainable, peaceful, and prosperous human development/ evolution is potentially threatened by uncontrollable productivity/ growth/ complexity that results in environmental and social overexploitation, ideological rigidity/ aggression, and related neighbouring imbalances/ inequalities on all levels of life. (*Threats by Uncontrollable Polycrisis*)

12) A general awareness has to arise in governments and international institutions that archaeologists are advisory partners in understanding past experiences, helping to reduce the consequences of unsustainable social, economic, environmental and cognitive developments and climate deterioration. Archaeologists have a ‘natural’ mandate for translations from the past, which has to be embedded into the decision-making on humankind's peaceful, sustainable and productivity-controlling presence and future, supervised by serious and robust governance bodies combatting/ balancing global inequality and lacks of respect for nature and regional cognitive distinctiveness. (*Archaeologists as Advisory Partners to Governance Bodies*)

Hans Georg K. Gebel

ex oriente at Berlin Free University
hggebel@zedat.fu-berlin.de

Endnotes

¹ The title of this contribution is borrowed from Mehmet Özdoğan. He told the true story of a foreign anthropological team showing a film about current (western) life to an indigenous audience and then asked them what they had seen and how they assessed what they had seen. After some perplexity about the question, one of the viewers said: “The chicken is very thin!” And many other spectators strongly agreed with him. The answer was initially incomprehensible until the anthropologists watched their film again: Indeed, a chicken was running briefly through a scene ... The story illustrates nicely that we only recognise what we know and experience. Is it the same with our cognitive ability to learn from history?

² The Bosphorus Summits in Istanbul represent “annual platforms for dialogue and collaboration, fostering partnerships and addressing challenges facing the region and the world.” The international economic and political forum brings together government officials, business leaders, academics, and other stakeholders to discuss various current issues related to the regional and global economy, politics, and business. The Bosphorus Summits' concept parallels only on a very superficial level the Davos World Economic Forums. They are not “showish” in their sense, and they celebrate more the direct dialogue at eye-level among participants by promoting the perspectives of the “Global South”, including Muslim countries and developing parts of the world. One of the guiding thoughts of the 2023 Bosphorus Summit was that the world is reaching an abyss due to the large number, extent, and acceleration potentials of conflicts, the globally advancing disregard for human rights, and the inability and obduracy of the systems to counter developments. The bloodshed of the Gaza/ Israel conflict directly influenced the content of many contributions to the Summit.

³ Mehmet Özdoğan, Barbara Helwing and I were invited to speak on the panel *The Consequences of Neolithic Lifeways*; the panel was moderated by Ali Ertenü from the International Cooperation Platform of the Summit, Istanbul,

standing in for Necmi Karul. We speakers introduced the topic to a large audience from various perspectives (M. Özdoğan from the Anatolian evidence, B. Helwing from the later city-states' development, and Gebel from a present-day focus).

⁴ It should be pointed out, however, that demands for a fundamentally apolitical state of archaeological research should be differentiated: Do they refer to empiric studies only, their interpretation, or to 'translated' lessons from the past?

⁵ Key institutions acknowledging or even advocating for an archaeopolitical mandate are the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA), the Climate Heritage Network (CHN), and the Society for American Archaeology (SAA). These institutions primarily contribute perspectives from the past on the current climate change debates.

References

- Connerton P.
1989 *How societies remember. Themes in the Social Sciences.* Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- European Association of Archaeologists (EAA)
2021 EAA 2021 Kiel Statement on Archaeology and Climate Change. <https://www.e-a-a.org/2021Statement>
- Fischer D.H.
1970 *Historians' fallacies: Toward a logic of historical thought.* New York: Harper and Row.
- Gebel H.G.K.
2021 Translating the past. The archaeological dimensions. In: A. Abar et al. (eds.), *Pearls, politics and pistachios. Essays in anthropology and memories on the occasion of Susan Pollock's 65th Birthday*: 611-623. Berlin: ex oriente.
- Hodder I.
2018 *The entanglements of humans and things: a long-term view.* In: I. Hodder, *Entangled: An Archaeology of the Relationships Between Humans and Things*: 158-178. Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Kahneman K.
2011 *Thinking, fast and slow.* New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux.
- Knapp A.B. and Ashmore W.
1999 *Archaeology, agency, and the social responsibilities of practitioners.* *American Anthropologist* 101.1: 152-153.
- Kristiansen K.
2014 *Toward a new paradigm? The Third Science Revolution and its possible consequences in archaeology.* *Current Swedish Archaeology* 22.1: 11-34.
- MacMillan M.
2008 *The uses and abuses of history.* Joanne Goodman Lecture Series. Toronto: Viking Canada.
- Van der Leeuw S.
2007 *Information processing and its role in the rise of the European world system.* In: R. Costanza, L.J. Graumlich and W. Steffen (eds.), *Sustainability or collapse? An integrated history and future of people on earth*: 213-241. Cambridge (Massachusetts): MIT Press.
- Zimmerman L.J.
2014 Public archaeology and the need for a public mandate. In: N. Merriman (ed.), *Public Archaeology*: 153-161. London: Routledge.